

DEVELOPMENT OF OXIDATION RESISTANT C/C - AND C/SiC - COMPOSITES BY COATING AND INFILTRATION

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ABSTRACT

Protective silicon carbide and nitride-based ceramic coatings are prepared from preceramic polymers. According to this route substrates like C/SiC composites are at first coated with slurries made of organosilicon polymers and fillers like ceramic or metal powders by dip-coating which represents a rapid and economical process. The adherent polymer/filler layers are then pyrolyzed into dense and crack-free ceramic coatings resulting in an increased oxidation resistance of the composite materials. Additionally, the infiltration of C/C composite materials by solutions of organosilicon polymers yielding a material with reduced porosity after pyrolysis is described.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced composites are excellent lightweight structural materials for high temperature applications, for example in aerospace industry as well as in energy and automotive technology. However, these composites oxidize very rapidly in air at temperatures above 400 °C. Therefore, these materials need an additional protective coating which effectively prevents oxidation.

Protective coatings can be prepared by CVD, sputter and spray processes, for instance. A promising alternative for manufacturing such coatings is the pyrolysis of preceramic compounds. According to this route, substrates like carbon fibre reinforced SiC composites are at first coated with preceramic polymers. These precursors are then pyrolyzed around 1000 °C yielding a ceramic coating which will be discussed in this paper.

POLYMER-DERIVED NONOXIDE CERAMICS

The Pyrolysis of preceramic compounds like organosilicon polymers provides a means for the preparation of silicon nitride- and silicon carbide-based nonoxide ceramics [1, 2, 3]. At first, preceramic polymers are synthesized from monomer units. After subsequent crosslinking of

these polymers into two or threedimensional networks the materials are converted into ceramic materials (organic/inorganic transition) by heat treatment around 1000 °C in inert atmosphere. If the temperature is raised further the obtained amorphous solids transform into crystalline materials.

The specific properties of precursor materials, like solubility, fusibility or viscosity, can be influenced by synthesis and crosslinking of the preceramic polymers, which creates a variety of shaping procedures and processing applications. Highly crosslinked infusible polymers are used for the preparation of ceramic monoliths [4]. Soluble and fusible polymers with appropriate viscosities can be applied for the preparation of ceramic coatings (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Preparation of ceramic coatings and monoliths by pyrolysis of preceramic polymers.

PREPARATION OF CERAMIC COATINGS

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

For the preparation of ceramic coatings polysilazanes [5] are used. These polymers can be pyrolyzed to amorphous silicon carbonitrides ($\text{Si}_x\text{C}_y\text{N}_z$) at 1100 °C in nitrogen or argon atmosphere [6]. Additionally, different gaseous reaction products like methane, ammonia, and hydrogen are split off during the conversion of the polymer into the ceramic (eq. 1):

R = CH₃, C₂H₅, C₂H₃

The polymers are dissolved in toluene. To this solution silicon powder (Elcem) with $d_{90} < 3\mu\text{m}$ is added and dispersed by ultrasonic mixing and intensive stirring. The obtained slurry is used for the dip-coating procedure (see below).

Two dimensional ($0^\circ/90^\circ$) C/SiC samples ($20 \times 10 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$) produced by liquid silicon infiltration of a C/C preform [7] are used as substrates. The substrates are ground using $65 \mu\text{m}$ diamond emery paper, cleaned in toluene and finally heated in vacuum (10^{-2} mbar) up to 900°C .

Dip-Coating

Dip-coating is well-known from the sol-gel technique for the preparation of oxide films and allows rapid and economic coating.

This technique was applied for the preparation of nonoxide ceramic coatings on C/SiC substrates (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Dip-coating process of C/SiC substrates

During this process the substrate is dipped into the polymer solution and withdrawn with a certain velocity v in a glove box under inert atmosphere. The thickness of the adsorbed polymer layer can be varied by changing the velocity v as well as the viscosity of the solution [8]. After the coating procedure the adsorbed layer is pyrolyzed under inert atmosphere to a ceramic coating.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Because of the change in density during the conversion of the polymer (density $\approx 1 \text{ g/cm}^3$) to the amorphous ceramic (density $\approx 2.4 \text{ g/cm}^3$) a volume shrinkage occurs during pyrolysis. Therefore, it was impossible to produce crack-free coatings with thickness in the range of several microns in one dip-coating-pyrolysis step. In Fig. 3 a typical result of a dip-coating experiment applying a solution of 67 wt% polyhydridomethylsilazane in toluene after pyrolysis at 1100°C is shown.

Figure 3. SEM micrograph of a ceramic coating on a C/SiC substrate prepared by a dip-coating process with a solution of 67 wt% polyhydridomethylsilazane in toluene and subsequent pyrolysis.

In a newly developed process we produced dense and large area ceramic coatings by adding fillers to the polymer solution in order to reduce shrinkage during pyrolysis. For that purpose ceramic powders like silicon nitride or silicon carbide are applied. Moreover, metal powders which react with the solid and gaseous pyrolysis products by volume extension have been used.

The filler content has to be chosen to such an extent that the shrinkage of the coating during pyrolysis is minimized but the viscosity of the slurry consisting of polymer and filler is suitable for applying a dip-coating process.

Fig. 4 shows a ceramic coating on a C/SiC substrate prepared by using a 60 wt% solution of polyhydridomethylsilazane in toluene which contains silicon powder as a filler with a content of 45 vol% (related to the polymer volume). The withdrawal speed during the dip-coating process is 2.7 cm/min. As can be seen from Fig. 4 dense and crack-free ceramic layers with a thickness up to 10 μm are obtained after pyrolysis at 1000 °C.

The adhesion of the ceramic layers is determined by the direct-pull-method, i. e. a stamp is attached to the layer and pulled off by a force perpendicular to the substrate surface [9]. Values up to 13 MPa have been measured by this method. Because of the excellent adhesion the layers are not pulled off but the substrate is broken which means that the real value is higher than 13 MPa.

Figure 4. SEM micrograph of a coated C/SiC substrate (cross-section) obtained by dip-coating with a slurry consisting of a 60 wt% solution of polyhydridomethylsilazane in toluene which contains 45 vol% silicon powder and subsequent pyrolysis at 1100 °C.

OXIDATION BEHAVIOUR OF THE CERAMIC COATINGS

In Fig. 5 the thermogravimetric investigation up to 1000 °C in air (10⁵ MPa, heating rate 1 K/min) of a coated C/SiC-sample (see Fig. 4) and a sample without coating is shown.

Figure 5. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) in air up to 1000 °C.

As can be seen from the diagram the sample without coating exhibits a weight loss of more than 50 % whereas the coated sample shows a weight loss of only 30 %. From the cross sections in

Fig. 6 and 7 it can be seen that all carbon fibres are burned out in the case of the sample without coating (Fig. 6) while the fibres in the case of the coated sample are still present (Fig. 7).

Figure 6. SEM micrograph of a C/SiC sample without coating after oxidation in air

Figure 7. SEM micrograph of a coated C/SiC sample after oxidation in air

The time until all carbon was burned out, i. e. the time until no further mass loss occurs is determined by TGA at 1160 °C in air (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Thermogravimetric analysis at 1160 °C in flowing air.

Figure 8 reveals that the life time of the C/SiC composite material can be enhanced up to 120 % by a coating with a thickness around 20 μm obtained after 4 coating-pyrolysis cycles.

INFILTRATION OF C/C PREFORMS

C/C preforms which are used for the preparation of C/SiC composites (see above) cannot be coated directly by dip-coating because of their high open porosity between 16 - 18 %. Infiltration of these materials with polysilazane solutions in vacuum below 10^{-2} mbar and subsequent pyrolysis provides a means to reduce the porosity of these materials and to produce an inner oxidation protection made of silicon carbonitride. Applying this process the open porosity of the materials can be reduced to 3 % after 5 infiltration-pyrolysis cycles.

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